

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B154
 Date: 20 Dec 2005
 Take Off: 10:50:10
 Landing: 14:07:31
 Flight Time: 3h 17m 21s

Campaign: Wet Neph
Operating Area: North Sea coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Direct Flight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manger	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Dropsondes	Paul James	FAAM
8	MARSS/DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
9	Wet Neph	Simon Osborne	Met Office
10	Wet Neph u/t	Martin Glew	Met Office
11	CCM2	Jo Green	Direct Flight
12	CPI	Martin Gallagher	Manchester University
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b154
 Date: 20 dec 2005
 Project: pre DABEX wet neph
 Location: Southern North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
103409		INU	-.10 kft	124	to NAV
105010		T/O	0.46 kft	217	Cranfield
105450		asp	5.0 kft	055	open
112410		video	10.0 kft	358	#1 dfc, #2 ffc
112651	114129	Profile 1	10.0 - -.08 kft	329	250'
113014		!	7.0 kft	322	JW power cycled - sti ll us
113339		rod	4.0 kft	319	500'/min
113734		qnh 1024	1.9 kft	317	
114129	115131	Run 1.1	-.08 - -.07 kft	318	250'
114218		bbr	-.09 kft	316	retract
115145		Heiman cal	0.09 kft	306	
115256	120257	Run 1.2	-.06 kft	147	250' to 4000'
120257	120747	Profile 2	-.06 - 3.7 kft	145	250' to 4000'
120415		bbr	0.98 kft	142	extend / reset
121043	122050	Run 2.1	3.7 kft	327	bbr retract 4000'
122051	122236	Profile 3	3.6 - 2.7 kft	319	4000' - 3000'
122424	122902	Run 3.1	2.7 kft	157	3000'
122902	123234	Profile 4	2.7 - 0.72 kft	145	3000' - 1000'
123234	123541	Run 4.1	0.72 - 0.71 kft	145	1000'
123321		bbr	0.73 kft	146	retract
123718	124733	Run 4.2	0.73 - 0.58 kft	331	
124733	124814	Profile 5	0.58 - 0.17 kft	316	
124955	125955	Run 5.1	0.17 - 0.19 kft	133	
130116	130155	Profile 6	0.17 - -.09 kft	311	250'
130155	131500	Run 6.1	-.09 - -.08 kft	313	250'
131618	133120	Run 6.2	-.08 - -.10 kft	134	250'
133007		heimann	-.07 kft	151	cal
133204		!	1.2 kft	152	end of science
140731		Land	-.08 kft	213	Cranfield
141231		INU	-.08 kft	307	52' 03.81N 000' 38.13
141329		GPS	-.08 kft	307	52' 04.36N 000' 37.50

B154 Track 20-DEC-05

FAAM Sortie Brief

Pre-DABEX clear skies test flying

Flight No: B154

Date: 20 Dec 2005

Trial objectives:

To test radiometers and aerosol sampling equipment that are essential to the DABEX campaign (Jan-Feb '06). These instruments include: (1) wet neph, (2) BBRs, (3) PCASP.

Location:

Southern North Sea.

Weather:

Cloudless skies, stable anticyclonic conditions; ideally advection of pollution over the sea.

Flight pattern: (subject to revision regarding SWS and BBR testing requirements)

1. Take off from base.
2. Transit out to operating area at FL100 [30 mins]
3. Profile descent to min altitude (250ft) [15mins]
4. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at lowest permitted altitude over sea [22 mins].
5. Profile ascent to 5000ft (or other level to be decided by mission scientist) at rate of 500ft/min [10mins]
6. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 5000ft [22 mins].
7. Profile descent to 2000ft (or other level to be decided by mission scientist) at rate of 500ft/min [5mins].
8. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 2000ft [22 mins].
9. Profile descent to 500ft (or other level to be decided by mission scientist) at rate of 500ft/min [5mins].
10. Two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 500ft [22 mins].
11. Transit back to base [30mins, total 183mins]
12. Land at base.

Aircraft Scientist's Debrief

Flight No: B154

Date: 20/12/2005

Pre-DABEX – Wet Neph test flight

The sortie was planned to allow the Wet Neph to sample the industrial aerosol being advected from the North East coast of England into the North Sea. It was decided to only load the aircraft with sufficient fuel for 3.5 hours so that a recovery to Cranfield could be made earlier if there were instrumentation problems.

The aircraft departed Cranfield at 10:50 and climbed to the transit at FL100 passing through the bases of a good deck of Sc at 4600 ft and the tops at 4900 ft. On reaching the operating area a profile was conducted from FL100 to 250 ft which encountered the Sc between 6400 and 4700 ft. Once below the cloud it could be seen that there was a pollution haze advecting from the Middlesbrough to Newcastle stretch of coast line while to the south of this there was heather burning taking place on the moor land in land from Whitby. This biomass burning aerosol was also being advected into the operating area.

We then conducted two straight and level runs at 250ft of 10 mins. each turning onto reciprocal between them. Elevated CO concentrations were noted at the northern end of the operating area and PCASP reported aerosol. During these two runs the Wet Nephelometer was unserviceable.

The end of the second run was coincident with the start of a profile to 4000 ft, this level selected to be below the cloud base, and during this profile the Wet Neph began working again.

Runs were then conducted at 4000 ft and 3000 ft with no aerosol detected so it was decided to abandon the run at 3000 ft and profile down to 1000 ft and position to the south to encounter the biomass burning plume. A further run northwards at 1000 ft encountered both the biomass plume and the industrial aerosol. PCASP concentrations were highest at around 5200 in the biomass plume.

A further run was then undertaken at 500 ft followed by two at 250 ft. All of these runs encountered both the industrial pollution and the biomass plume. The run at 500 ft and the first run at 250 ft also encountered an exhaust plume from a large ship which coincided with a peak in CO readings.

The recovery to Cranfield was started at the end of the final run at 250 ft.

Overall the sortie provided a useful shakedown of the Wet Neph although some problems remained.

David Pollard

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...154**.....

 Date ...**20/12/05**.....

 Page**1**..... of ...**4**..

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:54		4600ft			Under based at 4100ft
10:55		4900ft			Through tops
					Good deck of Sc,
					7/8 Cs or As above
11:05:50					Break in Sc deck below
					still Cs or As above
11:17:30		FL100	004	53.5N 0.6E	7/8 Sc ^{below} above
					Cs or As above thinning
11:23:49		100	358	53.9.000	8/8 Sc below.
					8/8 Cs and As thinning
11:26:20					QNH 1019
11:26:51	P1	FL100	328	54.1N 0E	down 1000ft/min
					Good deck of Sc in operating area.
11:31:02		6400		54.3N 0.3W	In cloud tops
11:32:50		4700			Base 20 - water droplets
11:33:24					Change to 500ft
					Good pellets very close to surf
					Heather burning even in sheltered
					places coming off whole
					feasible area.
11:32:25					QNH 1024
11:41:29	M/211	250ft	318	54.9N 0.3W	
11:46:30					Becoming drier above 600
11:51	R1-1	250ft			ended

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B. 154**.....

Date **20/12/5**.....

Page **2**.... of **4**....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:52:50	R1.2	250	148	55.2 1.4W	CO height at this end 2D reported aerosol
11:55:40					CO dropping off course of 5
11:58					peak in CO
					Web depth still incp
2103					Lovely path ^{ns} here all around
12:02:52	R1.2 P2	250	146	54.8 0.8W	start and end to 4000 ft
12:08:1	P2	4000ft	144	54.6 0.5W	Web depth working
17:08					repositioning S. dist for
12:09				54.5 0.4	Turning onto track
12:10:43	R2.1	4000			2D no aerosol
12:12:5					Some precip
12:20					Some scats SE below
12:20:4	R2.1/P3	4000	319	54.9 1.1	end of run to 3000 ft
12:22:36	P3	3000			end of profile
					turning over low cloud onl.
					southbound leg
12:24:24	3.1	3000	159		Start of run, reasonably clear below
12:28:02	3.1 P4	3000 1000 ft	145		Dropping to get into aerosol
12:32:34	P4 2.1	1000ft	145	54.6 0.6	short run south to see
					business burning aerosol
					2D = 2000 aerosol (from n 80)
12:35:41	4.1	1000			end just some cent of
					business burning plume
					2D aerosol conc dropped to 28%

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.154**.....
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **20/12/1**.....

 Page **3**... of **4**...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:37:19	4.2	1000	331		Start of (Dmin run 11) initially in Biomass burning plume 20-4200
12:38:50					20-5200
12:39:55					Seems to be leaving Biomass plume and leading towards a good layer of industrial stuff
	4.2 RH	1000	316		End of run, dropping to 500ft in same flow
	PL				Turning onto recip
	R5				
12:40:55	R5	500	122	54.9, 1.1	
12:49					A beam super tanker ^{100 up} low level patch just to W
12:49:29					into Biomass plume 20 - values up CO-up 20 near at 5800
12:59:55	R5	500			cut
13:01:16	R6	500	312	54.9 0.4	P down to 250ft
13:01:55	R6	250ft	314	54.5 0.4W	Start of run in Biomass CO increasing 20 - peak in biomass plume @ 0200
13:05:38					A beam super tanker again
13:06:14					CO slowly creeping up
13:08					W 20 - lots of structure

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Sci 2

Flight No **B**.....154.....
FAAM © 2004

Date 20/12/05.....

Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
105132 105132					Take off Garfield.
105505		~5000ft			In cloud
					2D seeing ice columns.
		~10000ft	003		Above ^{SLW} cloud. 2 Ci Above. ~ 7/8 thin
					SLW ~ 6/8 v. thin
					Wet neph reporting problems with inst + comp communications.
112651	P1	FL100	326	54.1/6.1	Probable descent along coast
113059		6200ft	320	54.4/10.4W	In top of cloud. (8/8 SLW)
					2D only seeing water drops supercooled liquid. at top
					Cloud base:
113312		~4300ft			2D confirms
113337		4000ft			Changing rate descent to 500ft/min
					Can see pollution from Teeside.
					-Smoke + haze.
113712		2000ft	317	54.6/10.7W	Air misting, some heavy cloud.
114129	P1 lead	250ft	318		Limited min alt due to pilots.
" "	R1.1	250ft	317	54.7/10W	
114830				55.2/1.3W	Clearing skies above, ~ 2/8 Ci above only
					At this end of run
~1149					Increase in pollution + CO.
	R1 lead	250ft			End of run
					Wet neph still not working.
115256	R1.2	250ft	147	55.2/1.4W	Reciprocal run.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.154**.....

 Date **20/12/05**.....

 Page **2** of **5**.....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:02:57	R1-2end	2500ft.	142	54.8/0.8W	End of run
" "	P2	2500ft.			Profile climb to 4000ft.
120429		1300ft.			Lat repd repeating nothing Ok.
120747	P2end	4000ft.	145	54.5/0.5W	Heading 5 to get bearing, planes from Teeside.
					Turning right.
121043	R2.1	4000ft.	324	54.5/0.5	Straight + level below 500 base
					2D not seeing any aerosol, but occasional water drop.
122051	R2.1	4000ft.	319	54.9/1.1W	Run end
" "	P3	4000ft.			Profile descent to 3000ft.
					Some W at ~2000ft at Mend. 1/8 G above.
122236	P3end	3000ft.			Right turn.
122424	R3.1	3000ft.	159	55.0W/1.1W	Coming through occasionally hazy patch.
					2D not seeing any aerosol.
122902	R3/lead	3000ft.	145	54.7/0.8W	terminating early. to save time.
" "	P4	3000ft.	143		descent to get into aerosol
					looks like being trapped below ^{BL} 1000ft.
123130		1200ft.	144	54.6/0.6	PUPP seeing 18/1cc aerosol.
123234	P4end	1000ft.	145	54.6/0.6	End profile descent.
" "	R4.1	1000ft.			Start of run
123352		1000ft.	144	54.5/0.5W	aerosol 2000 cc (max 3500)
					10 increased to 2.37 ppb
123544	R4/lead	1000ft.		54.4/0.4	Right turn reciprocal.

T 7.21, TD 1.26

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.154**.....
FAAM © 2004

Date **20/12/05**.....

Page **3** of **5**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123715	R62	1000ft.	331	54.4/0.5W	Heading NW
123759					CO increasing 500 → 565 ppb
123840					4200 cc aerosol
123852				54.5/0.5	5200 cc → CO 1010 ppb
123942		1000ft.	324	54.5/0.6	CO 556 ppb. → ambient again
124142				54.6/0.7	Cloud increasing overhead
124258					2D 250cc } short time only CO ↑ 1000 ppb.
124733	R62id	1000ft.	315	54.8/1.0W	End in.
	P5	1000ft.			Profile descent to 500ft.
124814	P5ad	500ft.	313	54.9/1.1	Turn left for reciprocal.
124956	P5.1	500ft.	133	54.8/1.1	2D 700 cc
					Wet neph seeing aerosol. CO 555 ppb
125457		500ft.	149	54.5/0.7	Down wind from Super tanker CO ~1400 ppb. max. + dip in O ₃ aerosol ~800 cc max.
125558					Back to normal
125711					Bio mass hazy plume CO 539 increasing
125803				54.5/0.5	PLASP 3000 → CO 774 ppb.
125847					CO max 1031
					decreasing again.
					PLASP Max 5200
125955	R5.1ad	500ft.		54.4/0.4W	End of in. other side of plume

BIO MASS BURNING

POLLUTION

BIO MASS BURNING

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B..154**.....

 Date **20112105**.....

 Page **4** of **5**.....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130116	P6	500ft			Profile descent to 250ft-
130155	P6 end	250ft-	312	54.5/0.4	
" "	R6.1	250ft-	312		Run heading NW
					CO increasing going thro' plume
					max 1100 ppb.
					max 6700cc PCASP
130616		250ft-	312	54.7/0.7W	CO starting to rise
130726					CO peaks 1800 ppb. (sharp peak)
					PCASP max 1600cc
130815					Sharp peak, CO: 1900 ppb
130840					CO 535 ambient again.
131420				55.0/1.2	PCASP 666, CO 789 ppb. + increasing (CO peak 1000 ppb.)
131500	R6.1 end	250ft-		55.0/1.3W	
131618	R6.2	250ft-	135	55.0/1.3W	Heading SE. CO max 1000 ppb.
					just S of end of run.
					PCASP variations during run ~ 1000cc
132240				54.7/0.8W	CO 404 drop, increasing to
132330					CO shot up to 1500+, short time
132400					CO 777. (in hazy layer)
					variable CO + PCASP conc during run.
132530				54.6/0.6	All back to normal.
132700		250ft-	145	54.5/0.6	Into biomass plume (v. hazy)

biomass amount of pollution?

pollution?

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.154**.....

 Date **20/12/2005**.....

 Operator's name: **M. GLEW/S. OSBORNE**.....

 Page) of **2**....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
Pre-flight								Neph ok; some ^{100%} discrepancy with RH sensors; chiller ok, but still not talking with LABVIEW.
1100	Transit							Can't talk to neph. Shut down nephs/hub/computer
1105								RH sensors fine, flow rate recording, not talking to nephelometers
1110								Neph/hub/computer off/on - Talking to wet neph, not dry. Wet neph RH 60%, RH down stream 20%.
1115								off/on, not talking to either neph.
1126								off/on, Talked to wet neph
1131								off/on, no neph
1135								off/on, reset comport to 2. Talking to dry neph not wet.
								RH1 30, RH2 37, RH3 20 RH5 58
								reboot just software, only talking to dry neph.
1141								off/on, talking only to dry.
1146								off/on, not talking to anything - any neph.
1149								nephelometers changed to ports 3 & 4 - off/on, neither neph
1200								dry port 1, wet port 2. off/on
1202								both neph working? Chiller set to +5°C Flow 1.02/min
1205								9 44 57 ↓ 18.3
121043	2.1	4000'	4	34	50			↓ 15.7 Inch of water in the trap No aerosol

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.154**.....

 Date **20/12/2005**.....

 Operator's name: **Clew/Osborne**....

 Page **2** of **2**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1225	3.1	3000'	9	35	45	↑	+13	RHS spiking. T _{water} +15 at 12:26
122402	R4	3000'↓	9	36	53	↓	+10	chiller set to +15 at start of profile.
123234	R4.1	1000'	9.7	42	49	↓	+15.8	1231 RHS decreasing, T _{water} +8.5
1234		1000'				↑	+15	chiller set to +15
123541	R4.1 end	1000'	9.8	38	53	↑	+19	chiller set to +20
123718	R4.2	1000'	9.7			↑	+19.8	chiller set to +25. 1238 T _{water} +24.8
1240	R4.2	1000'	9.8	41	74	↑		chiller set to +30. T _{water} +29.6 at 12:41
1243	R4.2	1000'	9.9			↓	+27	chiller set to +5, T _{water} +17 at 12:46
	R5↓	1000'↓	9.9					T _{water} +14 at 12:48
124955	R5.1	500'	10.0	43	62	↓	+10	
1253	R5.1	500'				↑	+14	chiller set to +15. Trap full. Chiller off
1300	R5.1 end		9.9	41	59	?	?	chiller off
131500	R6.1 end	250'	10.0	47	62	?	?	1305 RHS spiking
131618	R6.2	250'	10.0	46	62			
1323								Pump off. trap opened + drained.
132340								chiller on
1324	R6.2	250'	9.6	42	63		+24	chiller set to +25
1327	R6.2	250'					+29	chiller set to +30
1332	END SCIENCE, 1 finger of water in trap, chiller off.							
1335	Draining system. 1350 software off, pump running till landing.							

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 154

Date: 20th December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JN02	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JN02	Y	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	N	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B154

Date: 20th December 2005

Instruments

1. SID 1 – working
2. PCASP – noisy at times
3. 2D-P noisy at high level, some contamination after t/o
4. 2D-C noisy at high level
5. FSSSP ok
6. SID 2 working, some noise
7. TAFTS not operated
8. ARIES not operated
9. SWS not operated
10. MARSS not operated
11. DEIMOS not operated
12. CPI working
13. JW zero pot is set to nearly full scale (fully clock), zero now stuck off scale (-ve) INSTRUMENT
US
14. 3025 took a long warm up and several restarts before ops normal
15. Wet Neph; problems with comms early on but eventually worked correctly

Aircraft

No power change-over call

Satcom H Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B154:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	
MARSS/Deimos	
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x forward Facing Cameras

2 x forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647

Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk